

Studies in Heterocyclic Compounds. Part II.

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In the first communication in this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 312) Sircar and De studied the properties of the diheterocyclic compounds obtained from 2:3-diaminophenazine (Ullmann and Mauthner, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 4902). In all the compounds described the two dissimilar heterocyclic nuclei were separated by a benzene ring, e.g., 4:5-phenazino-2-phenyliminazole.

The present investigation is a continuation of the work of Sircar and De (*loc. cit.*) and was undertaken with the object of studying how in compounds containing two dissimilar adjacent heterocyclic rings in their molecules, the properties of the different heterocyclic nuclei are affected by one another and how the properties of such compounds differ from those of the corresponding compounds in which the two heterocyclic rings are separated by a benzene ring.

$\alpha\beta$ -Diaminoquinoxaline (Bladin, *Ber.*, 1885, 18, 72), which already contains an azine ring was chosen as the starting material. The idea was to prepare diheterocyclic compounds through the two *ortho*-amino groups and to study the properties of the resulting bodies in the manner indicated before.

With this object $\alpha\beta$ -diaminoquinoxaline has been condensed with phthalic, naphthalic, camphoric and diphenic anhydrides and the *o*-benzoylene-, *o*-naphthoylene-, *o*-camphoroylene-, *o*-diphenoylene- $\alpha\beta$ -quinoxalinoiminazoles are obtained.

The quinoxaline has also been condensed in the presence of a solvent with a number of aldehydes and the following iminazoles have been prepared: 4:5-quinoxalino-2-phenyliminazole, 4'-methyl-, 4'-nitro-, 2'-hydroxy-, 3'-nitro-, 2':4'-dihydroxy-, 4'-methoxy-, -4'-dimethylamino-4:5-quinoxalino-2-phenyliminazoles, and 4:5-quinoxalino-2-furfuryliminazole.

If the condensations are carried out in the absence of any solvent iminazoles of the above type are not formed, but *N*-substituted iminazoles (*cf.* Ladenburg, *Ber.*, 1878, 11, 500, 1648; Hinsberg, 1896, 19, 2025; 1887, 20, 1585) are obtained by the condensation of one molecule of the diamine with two molecules of the aldehyde with the liberation of two molecules of water.

The following have been prepared in that way: 4:5-quinoxalino-1-benzyl-2-phenyliminazole, 4:5-quinoxalino-1-*o*-hydroxybenzyl-2-*o*-hydroxyphenyliminazole, and 4:5-quinoxalino-1-*p*-methoxybenzyl-2-*p*-methoxyphenyliminazole.

From the study of the properties of the complex heterocyclic compounds described it is found that in them, in most cases, the properties of the corresponding simpler heterocyclic bodies are to some extent modified. For example, the complex iminazoles are much less soluble in the commoner organic solvents than the corresponding simpler iminazoles, obtained from *o*-phenylenediamine. Again from a comparison of the properties of the heterocyclic compounds in which the two hetero-rings are adjacent to one another with those of the corresponding compounds obtained from 2:3-diaminophenazine (Sircar and De, *loc. cit.*), in which the two hetero-rings are separated by a benzene nucleus, it is found that in some of the properties there is a marked difference between the compounds of the two series, *e.g.*, the colours of the compounds of the former type are invariably lighter than those of the compounds of the latter type. A comparative statement of the colours of compounds of the two types is given below.

Names of the compounds,	Colour.
{ <i>o</i> -Benzylene- $\alpha\beta$ -quinoxalinoiminazole	Very light yellow
{ ,, ,, 2:3-phenazinoiminazole	Bright yellow
{ <i>o</i> -Naphthoylene- $\alpha\beta$ -quinoxalinoiminazole	Yellow
{ ,, ,, 2:3-phenazino- ,,	Bright yellow
{ <i>o</i> -Camphoroylene- $\alpha\beta$ -quinoxalino- ,,	Light dirty yellow
{ ,, ,, 2:3-phenazino- ,,	Yellow
{ 4:5-Quinoxalino-2-phenyliminazole	Yellow
{ 4:5-Phenazino- ,, ,,	Shining brown red
{ 3'-Nitro-4:5-quinoxalino-2-phenyliminazole	Yellowish white
{ ,, ,, 4:5-phenazino- ,,	Orange yellow
{ 4'-Methoxy-4:5-quinoxalino- ,,	Light orange yellow
{ ,, ,, 4:5-phenazino- ,,	Orange yellow
{ 4'-Dimethylamino-4:5-quinoxalino- ,,	Brownish yellow
{ ,, ,, 4:5-phenazino- ,,	Chocolate red

EXPERIMENTAL.

αβ-Diaminoquinoxaline.

It was obtained in the purest form and best yield by adopting the following procedure: To a solution of *o*-phenylenediamine (10 g.) in methyl alcohol (30 c.c.), cyanogen gas, generated by the addition of a concentrated solution of potassium cyanide to a copper sulphate solution and heating, was passed until the deposition of a yellow precipitate of the diaminoquinoxaline was complete. After separation of the precipitate the mother liquor was concentrated and cyanogen gas was again passed through it when a further yield of the yellow precipitate was obtained. The diamine crystallised from pyridine in light yellow rhombic plates, not melting below 300° (*cf.* Bladin, *loc. cit.*), yield 5 g.

o-Benzoylene-αβ-quinoxalinoiminazole.

The fused mass, obtained by heating an intimate mixture of *αβ*-diaminoquinoxaline (0.5 g.) and phthalic anhydride (0.5 g.) on the oil-bath at 200-20° for ½ hour, was allowed to cool and powdered. It crystallised from pyridine, on cautious addition of hot water, as very light yellow fibrous needles, m.p. above 300°. It is soluble in alcohol, acetone, chloroform, amyl alcohol, pyridine, nitrobenzene or acetic acid, but insoluble in ether, benzene, dilute acids, or alkalis. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid giving a red coloration. (Found: N, 20.47. C₁₆H₈O₂N₄ requires N, 20.59 per cent.).

The following three iminazoles were prepared and purified in the same way as and possess properties similar to the preceding compound.

o-Naphthoylene- $\alpha\beta$ -quinoxalinoiminazole, fine long yellow needles. (Found: N, 17.33. $C_{20}H_{10}ON_4$ requires N, 17.39 per cent.)

o-Camphoroylene- $\alpha\beta$ -quinoxalinoiminazole, light dirty yellow needles, m.p. 280°. (Found: N, 18.59. $C_{18}H_{18}ON_4$ requires N, 18.30 per cent.)

o-Diphenoylene- $\alpha\beta$ -quinoxalinoiminazole, brownish yellow minute needles. It gives green-yellow fluorescence in chloroform or alcohol solution. (Found: N, 16.24. $C_{22}H_{12}ON_4$ requires N, 16.10 per cent.)

4:5-Quinoxalino-2-phenyliminazole.

A mixture of $\alpha\beta$ -diaminoquinoxaline (0.5 g.), benzaldehyde (1 g.) dissolved in a small quantity of pyridine was heated under reflux for 1 hour. The excess of benzaldehyde was removed by sodium bisulphite and shaking with water. The separated iminazole was washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and water and finally crystallised from acetic acid in beautiful small yellow rectangular needles, m.p. 290° (with previous shrinking at 275°). It is insoluble in dilute hydrochloric acid in the cold but dissolves slowly in the warm acid. It is sparingly soluble in benzene, alcohol or acetone, and readily soluble in nitrobenzene, pyridine or acetic acid. It gives red coloration with strong sulphuric acid. (Found: N, 22.37. $C_{15}H_{10}N_4$ requires N, 22.76 per cent.)

The following iminazoles were prepared, except where otherwise mentioned, in the same way as and possess properties, except where otherwise stated, similar to the preceding compound. In majority of the cases the reaction was complete in $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. When equimolecular quantities of the diamine and the aldehyde were taken, the subsequent treatment with sodium bisulphite solution was not done. The condensation product separated from pyridine solution on dilution with water. They do not melt below 300°.

4'-Methyl-4:5-quinoxalino-2-phenyliminazole, from the diamine (0.5 g.) and *p*-tolylaldehyde (2 g.), separated from acetic acid as light brownish yellow pear-shaped needles. It is soluble in alcohol, pyridine, nitrobenzene, acetic acid, chloroform, or amyl alcohol. (Found: N, 21.14. $C_{16}H_{12}N_4$ requires N, 21.53 per cent.)

4'-Nitro-4:5-quinoxalino-2-phenyliminazole, from equimolecular proportions of the diamine and *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde, crystallised from dilute alcohol in shining red long rectangular plates. (Found: N, 23.73. $C_{15}H_9O_2N_5$ requires N, 24.05 per cent.).

3'-Nitro-4:5-quinoxalino-2-phenyliminazole, separated from alcohol in yellowish white needles. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with yellow coloration. (Found: N, 24.35. $C_{15}H_9O_2N_5$ requires N, 24.05 per cent.).

2'-Hydroxy-4:5-quinoxalino-2-phenyliminazole, from the diamine (0.5 g.) and salicylic aldehyde (2 g.), crystallised from acetic acid in brown needles. It dissolves in alkali and is also readily soluble in nitrobenzene, pyridine, alcohol or acetone. (Found: N, 21.23. $C_{15}H_{10}ON_4$ requires N, 21.37 per cent.).

2':4'-Dihydroxy-4:5-quinoxalino-2-phenyliminazole, obtained by the condensation of $\alpha\beta$ -diaminoquinoxaline and resorcylic aldehyde, crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles. It is soluble in alkali. It dissolves readily in nitrobenzene or amyl alcohol, but less readily in alcohol or acetone. (Found: N, 19.69. $C_{15}H_{10}O_2N_4$ requires N, 20.14 per cent.).

4'-Methoxy-4:5-quinoxalino-2-phenyliminazole, from the diamine (0.5 g.) and anisic aldehyde (2 g.), after being separated from the unreacted anisic aldehyde, crystallised from dilute pyridine as light orange-yellow hexagonal prisms. It gives violet yellow fluorescence when its alcoholic or pyridine solution is diluted with water. It is insoluble in chloroform and soluble in nitrobenzene or acetic acid. (Found: N, 20.58. $C_{16}H_{12}ON_4$ requires N, 20.29 per cent.).

4'-Dimethylamino-4:5-quinoxalino-2-phenyliminazole, from dimethyl-*p*-aminobenzaldehyde and the diamine, was obtained as brownish yellow rectangular plates. With strong sulphuric acid it develops a light yellow colour. (Found: N, 23.97. $C_{17}H_{13}N_5$ requires N, 24.22 per cent.).

4:5-Quinoxalino-2-furfuryliminazole, obtained in the usual way from diaminoquinoxaline (0.5 g.) and furfuraldehyde (5 g.), separated from acetic acid in light yellow brown rectangular plates. It exhibits violet yellow fluorescence when its alcoholic or pyridine solution is diluted with water. (Found: N, 23.19. $C_{13}H_5ON_4$ requires N, 23.73 per cent.).

4:5-Quinoxalino-1-benzyl-2-phenyliminazole.

α,β -Diaminoquinoxaline (0.5 g.) when heated with benzaldehyde (20 c. c.) for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hour, separated on cooling in brilliant yellow long pear-shaped needles, which after being washed with ether were sufficiently pure for further analysis, m. p. above 300° . It is insoluble in ether or benzene and soluble in pyridine, nitrobenzene or amyl alcohol. With strong sulphuric acid it gives a yellow coloration. (Found: N, 16.30. $C_{22}H_{16}N_4$ requires N, 16.16 per cent.).

4:5-Quinoxalino-1-o-hydroxybenzyl-2-phenyliminazole, prepared in the same way as the preceding compound from the diamine (0.5 g.) and salicylic aldehyde (20 c. c.) was obtained as yellow rectangular plates, not melting below 300° . It is insoluble in dilute acids or chloroform but soluble in alkalis, amyl alcohol, acetone, pyridine, nitrobenzene or acetic acid. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with a red coloration. (Found: N, 15.77. $C_{22}H_{16}O_2N_4$ requires N, 15.32 per cent.).

4:5-Quinoxalino-1-p-methoxybenzyl-2-p-methoxyphenyliminazole. — α,β -Diaminoquinoxaline (0.5 g.) and anisic aldehyde (15 c. c.) were heated together for 1 hour. The reaction mixture was then poured in a concentrated solution of sodium bisulphite. The tarry mass obtained solidified on standing. This was filtered, washed and finally crystallised from acetic acid in very light brownish yellow needles, m. p. $243-45^\circ$. Except that it is insoluble in alkalis, its other properties are like those of the preceding compound. (Found: N, 14.38. $C_{24}H_{20}O_2N_4$ requires N, 14.14 per cent.)*

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